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HOW THE SERVICE SECTOR INFLUENCE INDIAN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The services sector forms the backbone of social and economic development of any country. It has emerged as the largest and fastest-growing sectors in the world economy, making higher contributions to the global output and employment. The growth in services industries now serves as an essential index of a country's development. After Green revolution and Industrial revolution, the next popular revolution is seen in the field of services sector. A two decade ago when the Indian Government initiated the process of liberalization, the service sector witnessed a boom. A number of banks, hotels, insurance companies, construction companies, specialized services in the areas of health, transport, legal and management have come up to make their strong presence felt. With dynamic changes in Indian economy, especially after the economic reforms, India is poised to be a strong economy in the world and the services sector is playing a vital role in this process. In the current economic scenario, the services sector is here to stay as India is fast emerging as a global services hub. Contributing more than 55 percent to real GDP growth, services sector will continue to be the mainstay of the expansion of the economy with business services including IT and financial services, commodity services and

community services being the main growth drivers. Its contributions to the GDP and export earnings of the country as well as the tax revenue of the Government are going.

Key words: Services Sector, Retail, Banking and finance, Tourism, Insurance Penetration.

INTRODUCTION:

India is 13th in services output. The services sector provides employment to 27% of the work force and is growing quickly, with a growth rate of 7.5% in 1991–2000, up from 4.5% in 1951–80. It has the largest share in the GDP, accounting for 57% in 2012, up from 15% in 1950.^[82] Information technology and business process outsourcing are among the fastest growing sectors, having a cumulative growth rate of revenue 33.6% between 1997 and 1998 and 2002–03 and contributing to 25% of the country's total exports in 2007–08. The growth in the IT sector is attributed to increased specialization, and an availability of a large pool of low cost, highly skilled, educated and fluent English-speaking workers, on the supply side, matched on the demand side by increased demand from foreign consumers interested in India's service exports, or those looking to outsource their operations. The share of the Indian IT industry in the country's GDP increased from 4.8% in 2005–06 to 7% in 2008. In 2009, seven Indian firms were listed among the top 15 technology outsourcing companies in the world.

The Services Sector constitutes a large part of the Indian economy both in terms of employment potential and its contribution to national income. The Sector covers a wide range of activities from the most sophisticated in the field of Information and Communication Technology to simple services pursued by the informal sector workers, for example, vegetable sellers, hawkers, rickshaw pullers, etc. The following broad grouping of activities can be considered to form part of the Services Sector:

- A) Trade
- B) Hotels and restaurants
- C) Transport including tourist assistance activities as well as activities of travel agencies and tour operators
- D) Storage and communication
- E) Banking and insurance
- F) Real estate and ownership of dwellings
- G) Public administration and defense
- H) Other services including education, medical and health, religious and other community services, legal services, recreation and entertainment services

The Services Sector has been the most dynamic sector of the Indian economy, especially over the last ten years. Table 1 shows the changes that have been taking place in the Services Sector over the last few decades.

From a low level of 27.52 per cent of GDP in 1950-51, the share of services increased to 47.88 per cent in 1999-2000. Between 1950-51 and 1990-91, the share of Services Sector in GDP rose by only 13.07 percentage points, which is an increase of about 0.33 percentage points per annum. However, between 1990-91 and 1999-2000, the share had increased by 7.29 percentage points, which is an increase of 0.81 percentage points per annum. Clearly, the rate of growth is significantly higher in the 1990s.

Table 1: Sectoral Shares in GDP

(in per cent)

Year	Agriculture #	Manufacturing Y	Services*
1950-51	59.19	13.29	27.52
1960-61	54.74	16.61	28.65
1970-71	48.12	19.91	31.97
1980-81	41.82	21.59	36.59
1990-91	34.92	24.49	40.59
1991-92	34.08	23.93	41.99
1992-93	34.17	23.74	42.09
1993-94	33.54	23.69	42.77
1994-95	32.94	24.35	42.71
1995-96	30.58	25.47	43.95
1996-97	30.86	25.45	43.69
1997-98	29.03	25.20	45.77
1998-99	29.03	24.51	46.46
1999-2000	27.49	24.63	47.88

Notes: Among the following symbols,

includes forestry and logging, fishing, mining and quarrying;

Y includes construction, electricity, gas and water supply;

* includes (a) transport, communication and trade;

Services Sector:

A few decades ago when the Indian Government initiated the process of liberalization, the service sector witnessed a boom. A number of banks, hotels, insurance companies, construction companies, specialized services in the areas of health, transport, legal and management have come up to make their strong presence felt. Services were recorded as the fastest growing sector of the Indian economy in the last five years. In fact, certain sectors of services like the media and knowledge industries recorded as high as 30 to 40 percent annual growth in the last five years. The RBI Annual Report for 2008 - 2009 notes that service has emerged as the fastest growing sector and has imparted much of the resilience to the overall growth of the economy particularly in times of adverse agricultural shocks and industrial slow down. The share of services including construction in real GDP has increased from 43.7 percent in 1990-91 to 51.2 percent in 1999-2000 and 56.1 percent in 2007-08. A major part of the increase has taken place in trade, transportation, communication, and information technology, healthcare, banking and insurance sectors. The sector has come to play an increasingly dominant role in the economy accounting for 68.6 percent of the overall average growth in GDP in the last five years between 2003-04 and 2007-08. In its recent release of "State of the Economy Report", Confederation of Indian Industry (CII) expects the growth rate to continue apace with services sector expected to grow at a rate of 11.2 percent in 2009-10. The fact that the service sector now accounts for more than half the GDP takes the Indian economy closer to the fundamentals of a developed economy.

The **Economy of India** is the 10th-largest in the world by nominal GDP and the third-largest by purchasing power parity (PPP). Indian Economy is 2nd & 3rd largest in Asia in terms of PPP and Nominal GDP respectively & largest Economy in South Asia. It is the world's 2nd fastest-growing major economy just after China, with growth rates averaging 7.7% over the past 10 years.

India is one of the fastest developing Economic Superpower with potential to become world third largest economy (Nominal) by 2020.

The economy slowed to around 5.0% for the 2012–13 fiscal year compared with 6.2% in the previous fiscal but still remained the 2nd fastest growing Major Economy of G20 just behind China. According to Moody's, the Economic Growth Rate of India would be 5.5% in 2014-15. The government has forecast a growth rate of 6.1%–6.7% for the year 2013–14, whilst the RBI expects the same to be at 5.7%.

Services:

Retail:

Retail industry is one of the pillars of Indian economy and accounts for 14–15% of its GDP. The Indian retail market is estimated to be US\$ 450 billion and one of the top five retail markets in the world by economic value. India is one of the fastest growing retail market in the world, with 1.2 billion people. India's retailing industry essentially consists of the local mom and pop store, owner manned general stores, convenience stores, hand cart and pavement vendors, etc. Organised retail supermarkets account for 4% of the market as of 2008. Regulations prevent most foreign investment in retailing. In 2012 government permitted 51% FDI in multi brand retail and 100% FDI in single brand retail. Moreover, over thirty regulations such as "signboard licences" and "anti-hoarding measures" may have to be complied before a store can open doors. There are taxes for moving goods from state to state, and even within states.

Tourism:

Tourism in India is relatively undeveloped, but a high growth sector. It contributes 6.23% to the national GDP and 8.78% of the total employment. The majority of foreign tourists come from USA and UK. India's rich history and its cultural and geographical diversity make its international tourism appeal large and diverse. It presents heritage and cultural tourism along with medical, business and sports tourism. India has one of the largest and fastest growing medical tourism sectors.

Banking and finance:

The Indian money market is classified into the organised sector, comprising private, public and foreign owned commercial banks and cooperative banks, together known as *scheduled banks*, and the unorganised sector, which includes individual or family owned indigenous bankers or money lenders and non-banking financial companies. The unorganised sector and microcredit are still preferred over traditional banks in rural and sub-urban areas, especially for non-productive purposes, like ceremonies and short duration loans. Prime Minister Indira Gandhi nationalised 14 banks in 1969, followed by six others in 1980, and made it mandatory for banks to provide 40% of their net credit to priority sectors like agriculture, small-scale industry, retail trade, small businesses, etc. to ensure that the banks fulfill their social and developmental goals. Since then, the number of bank branches has increased from 8,260 in 1969 to 72,170 in 2007 and the population covered by a branch decreased from 63,800 to 15,000 during the same period. The total bank deposits increased from ₹59.1 billion (US\$990 million) in 1970–71 to ₹38309.22 billion (US\$640 billion) in 2008–09. Despite an increase of rural branches, from 1,860 or 22% of the total number of branches in 1969 to 30,590 or 42% in 2007, only 32,270 out of 500,000 villages are covered by a scheduled bank.

India's gross domestic saving in 2006–07 as a percentage of GDP stood at a high 32.8%.^[111] More than half of personal savings are invested in physical assets such as land, houses, cattle, and gold.^[112] The

public sector banks hold over 75% of total assets of the banking industry, with the private and foreign banks holding 18.2% and 6.5% respectively. Since liberalization, the government has approved significant banking reforms. While some of these relate to nationalized banks, like encouraging mergers, reducing government interference and increasing profitability and competitiveness, other reforms have opened up the banking and insurance sectors to private and foreign players.

Graphical depiction of India's product exports in 28 color-coded categories

Since liberalisation, the value of India's international trade has increased sharply, with the contribution of total trade in goods and services to the GDP rising from 16% in 1990–91 to 47% in 2008–10.^{[142][143]} India accounts for 1.44% of exports and 2.12% of imports for merchandise trade and 3.34% of exports and 3.31% of imports for commercial services trade worldwide.^[143] India's major trading partners are the European Union, China, the United States of America and the United Arab Emirates.^[144] In 2006–07, major export commodities included engineering goods, petroleum products, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, gems and jewellery, textiles and garments, agricultural products, iron ore and other minerals. Major import commodities included crude oil and related products, machinery, electronic goods, gold and silver.^[145] In November 2010, exports increased 22.3% year-on-year to ₹850.63 billion (US\$14 billion), while imports were up 7.5% at ₹1251.33 billion (US\$21 billion). Trade deficit for the same month dropped from ₹468.65 billion (US\$7.8 billion) in 2009 to ₹400.7 billion (US\$6.7 billion) in 2010.

India is a founding-member of General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) since 1947 and its successor, the WTO. While participating actively in its general council meetings, India has been crucial in voicing the concerns of the developing world. For instance, India has continued its opposition to the inclusion of such matters as labour and environment issues and other non-tariff barriers to trade into the WTO policies.

Foreign direct investment:

As the third-largest economy in the world in PPP terms, India is a preferred destination for FDI; During the year 2011, FDI inflow into India stood at \$36.5 billion, 51.1% higher than 2010 figure of \$24.15 billion. India has strengths in telecommunication, information technology and other significant areas such as auto components, chemicals, apparels, pharmaceuticals, and jewellery. Despite a surge in foreign investments, rigid FDI policies were a significant hindrance. However, due to positive economic reforms aimed at deregulating the economy and stimulating foreign investment, India has positioned itself as one of the front-runners of the rapidly growing Asia-Pacific region. India has a large pool of skilled managerial and technical expertise. The size of the middle-class population stands at 300 million and represents a growing consumer market.

During 2000–10, the country attracted \$178 billion as FDI.^[160] The inordinately high investment from Mauritius is due to routing of international funds through the country given significant tax advantages; double taxation is avoided due to a tax treaty between India and Mauritius, and Mauritius is a capital gains tax haven, effectively creating a zero-taxation FDI channel.

Life Insurance

There are 23 private-sector firms providing life insurance, who have commenced operations over the period 2000–10. The industry which reported in annual growth rate of 19.8% during the period 1996–97 to 2000–01 has, post opening up the sector reported in an annual growth rate of 23.4% during 2001–02 to 2010–11. There has been an average growth of 34% in the first premium in the insurance sector between 2001 and 2002 and 2010–11. The life insurers underwrote new business of Rs 1,26,381 crore during financial year 2010–11 as against Rs 1,09,894 crore during the year 2009–10, recording a growth of 15%. Of the new business premium underwritten, LIC accounted Rs 87012.65 crore (68.9% market

share). The market share of these insurers was 65.1% and 34.9% respectively in the corresponding period 2009–10.

Non-Life Insurance

The industry which reported a growth rate of around 10 percent during the period 1996–97 to 2000–10 has, post opening up the sector, reported average annual growth of 15.85% over the period 2001–02 to 2010–11. In addition, the specialized insurers Export Credit Guarantee Corporation and Agriculture Insurance Company (AIC) are offering credit guarantee and corp insurance respectively. AIC, which has initially offering coverage under the National Agriculture Insurance Company (NAIS), has now started providing crop insurance cover on commercial line as well. It has introduced several innovative products such as weather insurance and specific crop related products. The premium underwritten by the non life insurers during 2010–11 was Rs 42,576 crore as against Rs 34,620 crore in 2009–10. The growth was satisfactory, particularly in the view of the across the broad cuts in the tariff rates. The private insurers underwrote premium of Rs 17,424 crore as against rs Rs 13,977 crore in 2009–10. The public sector insurers on the other hand, underwrote a premium of Rs 25,151.8 in 2010–11 as against Rs 20,643.5 crore in 2009–10, i.e. a growth of 21.8% as against 14.5% in 2009–10.

Insurance Penetration

The growth of insurance sector is internationally measured based standard of insurance penetration. Insurance Penetration is defined as the ratio of premium underwritten in a given year to Gross Domestic Product. Likewise, insurance density is another well recognized benchmark and is defined as the ratio of premium underwritten in a given year to total population (measured in US dollars for convenience of comparison). The Indian insurance business has in the past remained under developed with low levels of insurance penetration. Post liberalization sector has succeeded in raising the levels of insurance penetration from 2.3 (life 1.8 and non life 0.7) in 2000 to 5.1 (life 4.4 and non life 0.7) in 2010.

CONCLUSION:

The services sector forms the backbone of social and economic development of any country. It has emerged as the largest and fastest-growing sectors in the world economy, making higher contributions to the global output and employment. With dynamic changes in Indian economy, especially after the economic reforms, India is poised to be a strong economy in the world and the services sector is playing a vital role in this process. In the current economic scenario, the services sector is here to stay as India is fast emerging as a global services hub. Contributing more than 55 percent to real GDP growth, services sector will continue to be the mainstay of the expansion of the economy with business services including IT and ITeS, financial services, commodity services and community services being the main growth drivers. Its contributions to the GDP and export earnings of the country as well as the tax revenue of the Government are increasing year by year since the last decade. This sector is, undoubtedly, providing strength to Indian economy in facing the global challenges. The services sector can continue to be the engine for development and growth of the economy provided some major policy changes are adopted by the Government of India. A proper policy framework on the lines of the industrial policy and agricultural policy can be an important step in this direction.

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